

OBEDIENCE

Gu ru 'phrin las ཀུ་རུ་འཕྲིན་ལས། (Gerichengli 格日成立)*

Black yak hair tents were pitched on each side of a creek that snaked through endless flat grassland. Yaks, sheep, and horses comfortably grazed along the brook. As a colt galloped to its mother, neighing with its tail in the air, a flock of lambs frolicked near the river. A lazy watchdog sprawled, barking mindlessly at the vigorous lambs. Prayer flags tied to the tops of two poles along a tent's entrance fluttered in a gentle breeze. A seven-year-old barefoot girl with messy hair emerged from the tent, curious to see why the watchdog was barking. She was short, so people called her Little Girl. She reentered the tent after glancing at the sleepy dog.

A woman with rough overworked hands took a kettle from the adobe stove in the middle of the tent and poured milk tea into Little Girl's wooden bowl. Little Girl sat by the woman and reported, "Mother, the dog barked at lambs running on the river banks."

"Finish your breakfast quickly and take the calves out to graze," her mother said.

Little Girl nodded while picking her bowl up from the ground, sipping some tea, and selecting a piece of fried bread from a green plastic basin beside her. Her mother walked outside as Little Girl munched on the bread. After breakfast, Little Girl got ready for the day. She pulled on her leather boots and wrapped herself in a sheepskin robe. Next, she poured milk tea into a battered army-green aluminum container, wrapped the neck with a piece of plastic, and tied it tightly with yak hair yarn to stop tea from seeping out. She poked two pieces of bread wrapped in plastic in her robe pouch and walked out of the tent.

Her mother had untethered the calves and tied them in pairs with strong short, yak hair ropes. When Little Girl came near, her mother asked, "Did you bring food?"

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Little Girl joyfully responded, "I brought bread and a bottle of milk tea. I'm going to have a splendid lunch today!"

Her mother tossed a piece of dried yak dung at a pair of calves that seemed ready to rush to where their mothers were grazing. The calves bolted when the dung bounced near them and ran to join the other calves.

"Drive those calves to a rich grassland, and don't let them run to their mothers and nurse!" Little Girl's Mother ordered.

Little Girl swung a slingshot over her head and responded, "Yes, Mother. Beat me if a calf nurses its mother today!"

Her mother stood and watched her daughter drive the calves to where neighbor children herded their family's calves.

Little Girl soon squirmed out of her robe and pulled off her shoes, unable to bear the scorching sunshine. She stretched her robe on the ground and lay on it, covering her head with her red sash but periodically checking on the calves to ensure none had joined their mothers far from where she was herding them.

A calf had rushed from the calves the day before and joined the other yaks while Little Girl was napping. Her mother had scolded her when she tried to milk the yak and realized its calf had nursed all the milk. Today, Little Girl vigilantly watched each calf's movement, sure her mother would not forgive her if she made the same mistake again.

At noon, Little Girl unwrapped the plastic and started eating lunch but noticed a pair of calves walking toward the family's other grazing yaks. She left the bread on her robe and ran to the calves in her red leggings and flapping fabric shirt. Once she got near, she picked up stones and hurled them at the two naughty calves, forcing them back to the other calves.

She returned, sprawled on her robe panting as beads of sweat gathered on her broad forehead and flowed down her cheeks onto her robe. After a few minutes, she raised her head and plucked flowers stuck between her toes. She took the aluminum container from under her robe and untied the yak hair thread. A drop of milk trickled down her chin, leaving a white streak as she gulped milk tea.

She belched after drinking and gobbled some bread.

In the distance, she saw two neighbor children watering their family's calves. They normally herded together. Little Girl decided to offer bread and milk tea to the neighbor boy if he herded calves with her. She took a sip of tea and bit a piece of bread, wondering why Big Head, as everyone called him, wasn't herding calves with her but with a neighbor girl. "Maybe Big Head is attracted to that girl because she has a nice voice and knows many songs. Her mother is a well-known local singer and taught her many songs. Big Head probably enjoys listening," she thought.

Little Girl drove her family's calves back home in the early evening. With her mother, they untied the calves from one another and tethered them to long ropes. Her mother clutched a calf's neck rope and pulled the calf to where other calves were tied. She tied the calf and told her daughter, "Go drive the mother yaks back."

"Yes, Mother," Little Girl replied.

Her empty tea bottle fell on the ground as she untied her sash. She tossed her robe and sash away and rushed to her family's yaks. As she ran, Little Girl could hear the mother yaks grazing near her family yak enclosure and their calves mooing to each other.

In the meantime, Little Girl's mother went into the tent, washing her hands after scooping water from a wooden bucket and pouring it into a basin. She opened a small, rectangular wooden box divided into three parts by two boards. One part contained a big piece of butter, one dried cheese, and the third roasted barley flour. She took a piece of butter from the big chunk and stuck it onto the upper part of her milking pail. She held the milking bucket in her right hand and a thick black and white yak hair rope in her left hand and went out.

Little Girl drove the mother yaks into the yak enclosure. Her mother placed the bucket on the ground and tethered the mother yaks. She then hobbled a mother yak with the black and white rope as Little Girl untied a calf.

The calf rushed to its mother and nursed crazily. Little Girl grasped the calf's neck rope when white foam appeared around its

mouth and tied it to the tether rope. She stood next to her mother, who sang milking songs while milking.

Little Girl drove the rest of the family's yaks and the horses home at sunset.

Dogs always barked aimlessly when darkness came. In the tent, mother and daughter ate meat soup and *rtsam pa* under the dim light of a flickering butter lamp. A small fire was burning in the stove. The noise of slurping soup broke the silence in the tent. Little Girl considered asking her mother something, but her mother's glum face made her swallow what she was about to say.

Little Girl slept on a dried yak skin beside her mother on one side of the tent. She snuggled into her sheepskin robe and another of her mother's robes. A folded robe covered with her sash was her pillow. Unable to sleep, she counted glistening stars in the blue sky through the hole in the top of their family's tent. Losing interest in the stars, she turned her head to her mother's side, asking, "Mother, are you still awake?"

Her mother covered her head with her robe and responded softly, "Yeah."

Little Girl was glad that she could ask the question on her mind. "Can you sing?"

After a pause, her mother said, "Yeah."

"Do you know many songs?"

"No, only a few."

"Is it hard to learn songs?"

Her mother murmured something she couldn't hear.

"What? I didn't hear clearly. Is it hard to learn songs? Can you teach me some songs?"

The mother turned, faced her daughter, and said, "Songs are easy to learn. I'm sleepy. Let me sleep. I'll teach you tomorrow night if you herd the calves well."

Little Girl broke into a big smile and let her mother sleep.

The following day, Little Girl drove her family's calves to the usual place where she often herded her calves. Later, the neighbor girl and boy joined her. The neighbor girl was taller than her peers

in their tribe, so locals called her Taller Girl. They herded the calves together and sat next to each other in a field of colorful flowers. Taller Girl picked a marsh marigold, sniffed, handed it to Big Head, and announced, "What a nice smell."

Big Head took it from her plump little hand, sniffed, and said, "You're right. The smell is really nice," and handed it back to Taller Girl, who said, "Keep it. I am giving it to you."

Big Head looked at the flower's petals and handed the flower to Little Girl. As Little Girl was ready to take it from Big Head, Taller Girl grabbed Big Head's hand, exclaiming, "I gave it to you, not ..."

Little Girl plucked a marsh marigold, showed it to Taller Girl, and declared, "I can pick flowers by myself."

Taller Girl squinted at Little Girl, said nothing, looked around, and picked a bunch of marsh marigolds. Big Head grasped Little Girl's hand when she wanted to pick more and said, "Don't pick flowers. You won't grow taller if you pick flowers. Whenever I tried to pick flowers, my grandmother said, 'If you pick flowers, you'll not grow as tall as your father because you kill the flowers when you pick them. A supernatural creature doesn't let you grow taller as punishment for killing the flowers.'"

Taller Girl giggled as Little Girl stopped picking flowers. Taller Girl picked more flowers, held them, and said, "I'm taller than you, so I don't need to worry about growing taller."

Little Girl's only response was to give her flowers to Big Head, who took them, paused a second, and returned them with, "You don't have any flowers, so keep them."

Big Head turned to Taller Girl and said, "We won't compare who has more flowers. We can play another game. Let's sing and see who the best singer is."

Taller Girl had a great voice and knew more songs than Big Head and Little Girl. She grabbed Big Head's arm and said, "Great, let's sing!"

Little Girl tilted her head in disagreement and glanced at Taller Girl's blunt nose, protruding cheeks, and small eyes. She then looked at Big Head's round fish eyes below his thick eyebrows and

sharp nose. She tried to say something to Big Head, but he didn't give her a chance, announcing, "Taller Girl, you sing first since you know many songs."

Taller Girl smiled, stood, tilted her head to the left, touched her left cheek with her left palm, held her right hand in the air, and sang mesmerizing Big Head and Little Girl.

One of Taller Girl's calves suddenly left the herd of calves and headed toward where the other yaks were grazing. Taller Girl stopped singing and quickly announced, "I have to drive the calf back into the herd of calves. My mother will scold me if it joins my family's yaks," and raced toward the calf.

Big Head stood and ran after her saying, "I'll help you!"

Little Girl watched and pondered, "Why did Big Head help her? Why did he not stay with me? Maybe she sings well, and he likes her."

A few hours later, they drove their calves back home.

At dusk, Little Girl and her mother noticed one of their yaks in Taller Girl's yak enclosure. Taller Girl's tall mother helped them drive the yak out from her family's enclosure. When they finished, Taller Girl's mother told Little Girl, "You and Taller Girl are relatives. You should like each other and never fight when you herd calves together."

Little Girl nodded and ran after her mother, who quickly drove the yak home. They tied it when they got home and walked into their tent.

Little Girl lit a butter lamp on her family's shrine table and recited mantras while her mother added fuel to the stove and put a pot on the stove. Little Girl looked at the pot and asked, "Mother, what's in the pot?"

"Leftover meat soup we cooked last night."

They went to bed after supper.

As usual, Little Girl slept next to her mother. She pulled her robe slightly over her head and said, "Mother, you promised to teach me songs last night. I herded calves well today."

"OK. What song do you want to learn?"

"I don't know any songs. Teach me whatever you know."

"I'll teach you a short song."

She sang two verses to demonstrate, turned to her daughter, and said, "Now, you sing them."

Little Girl cleared her throat and took a deep breath. Hearing her high-pitched voice, she stopped.

"Good, keep singing. You have a nice voice," her mother encouraged.

"Don't lie."

"No! You sing well."

Little Girl started singing hesitantly but soon stopped, confessing, "I forgot the lyrics."

Her mother repeated the lyrics several times and asked her to sing again. Covering her head with her robe, Little Girl tried to sing.

"Don't be silly! There's no reason to be shy with your mother."

Little Girl uncovered her head and said, "It's my first time to sing."

She cleared her throat again and sang the first verse, then stopped declaring she had forgotten the second verse again.

"Stupid girl. First, you should memorize the lyrics. Otherwise, how can you sing?" chastised her mother.

The mother repeated the lyrics several times before announcing, "Let's sleep. I'm sleepy. You can practice tomorrow."

Little Girl agreed, and while her mother soon snored beside her, she inaudibly repeated the lyrics.

The next day, the three calf herders were again having lunch together. Little Girl handed her milk tea container to Big Head and said, "Drink milk tea. You said you were thirsty."

Watching her big, dark eyes, Big Head took it from Little Girl and said, "My mother filled my tea container this morning, but I forgot to bring it with me."

As he gulped, tea coursed from his chin to his neck. The girls burst into laughter when he stopped drinking and dried his neck.

He returned the tea container to Little Girl and said, "I drank half of your tea. I was too thirsty."

Little Girl drank some of the tea and assured, "I'm not very thirsty, so it's OK."

Taller Girl fumbled in her robe pouch and eventually took out a piece of *rtsam pa* wrapped in a plastic bag. She placed it on her lap and continued groping in her robe pouch but found nothing. "I also forgot to bring my cup with me. May I drink a bit of your tea?"

Looking at Big Head, who was munching on a piece of baked bread, Little Girl said, "There's only enough tea for two."

Big Head picked up the tea container from the ground near Little Girl, handed it to Taller Girl, and exclaimed, "I'm not going to drink more. You two drink it!"

Taller Girl drank, then asked, "Who wants to eat *rtsam pa*? I'll give you a piece."

Big Head declined.

Little Girl shook her head and took a bite of her bun.

Glancing at their calves, Taller Girl said, "Our calves are busy grazing, so we can play games now. I sang yesterday. You two didn't. Now it's your turn."

Big Head and Little Girl looked at each other and smiled. Little Girl stuck out her tongue and said, "You sing first."

Big Head said, "You sing first, then I'll sing."

Little Girl put her head down, looked at the bun she held, and cleared her throat each time her herding mates encouraged her to start. Sweat gathered on her forehead and nose. Big Head encouraged, "Don't be shy. You must have a voice as nice as your mother's."

Little Girl replied without looking at Big Head, "I don't know any songs."

Taller Girl said, "You told me this morning your mother taught you a song last night."

Big Head said, "Sing the song you learned last night!"

Little Girl raised her head, smiled, and confided, "I forgot the

lyrics."

Big Head encouraged, "Well, just sing the part you remember."

Taller Girl checked in each direction, "Don't be reluctant. Nobody's watching."

Although trembling, Little Girl took a long breath and started singing. After the first verse, Taller Girl heartily laughed. Little Girl immediately stopped and covered her head with her hands. Big Head touched Little Girl's head, saying, "Keep singing. You have a lovely voice!"

"No, I'm not going to sing. Taller Girl was laughing," protested Little Girl.

Taller Girl said, "I wasn't laughing at you. You sing well."

Little Girl lifted her head a few seconds later, looked at Big Head, and announced, "It's your turn."

Big Head put the piece of baked bread on his lap into his robe pouch. Looking at the girls, he smiled, stood, and ran. Taller Girl's piece of round *rtsam pa* rolled onto the ground from her lap as she stood and chased Big Head. Little Girl watched, sure she would catch him and bring him back. Taller Girl grabbed his robe, causing him to fall. Big Head sprawled on the ground, looked at Taller Girl, and gestured for her to sit beside him.

Meanwhile, Little Girl finished eating the bun and drank the rest of her tea. She was still feeling very shy but grudgingly joined them.

That night, Little Girl and her mother sat near the stove with the only light in the tent provided by light from the stove.

"Let's go to bed. I have already taught you all verses."

Little Girl leaned against her mother and pleaded, "Let me practice again. I'm stupid and will forget the lyrics and melody."

"Practice tomorrow while herding the calves."

"Our neighbor boy said I have a good voice. I should learn more songs."

Little Girl's mother stood and said, "It's enough for you to know one song since you're not going to be a public singer. Singing

doesn't make you a good girl."

"What makes me a good girl?"

"A good girl herds calves and yaks well, is filial, obeys her parents in everything, respects elders, and doesn't gossip about others."

The two went out to pee and returned to their sleeping space. Little Girl, wrapped in her warm robes, began reciting song lyrics. Disturbed by her daughter's recitations, her mother demanded, "Let me sleep! Chant scriptures rather than recite lyrics."

"Yes, mother."

"Chant Sgrol ma mantras. You'll give birth to sons if you chant many Sgrol ma mantras."

"OK," Little Girl said, chanting a Sgrol ma mantra until she slept.

Big Head and Little Girl were again herding calves a few days later. Little Girl put her head down and sang:

Black yaks are the dew on grass tops of the mountain peaks
The yak herder is the cosmic sun

Big Head stared at her, intoxicated by her pleasant song. Little Girl stopped, "Oh, I can't remember the lyrics. Let me think," and continued a bit later:

Yearlings are the glittering stars in the sky
The shepherd is the milky full moon

Horses are the colorful flowers on the bank of the lake
The horse-herder is the inner jewel of the lake

Little Girl looked at Big Head as she finished singing. He smiled and complimented, "You sing well. Can you sing it again?"

She smiled and said, "I can sing it tomorrow."

Big Head insisted, "But I want to listen to it now. I enjoy

listening to your singing."

Coughing, Little Girl replied, "I can't sing it. My throat is not comfortable. I can sing it for you tomorrow."

Big Head looked into Little Girl's eyes and asked, "Promise?"

She nodded. Big Head smiled, thought a second, and said, "Tomorrow, my family will move to our autumn pasture."

Little Girl added, "My family will move to my family's pasture the day after tomorrow."

Big Head said sadly, "We can't see each other until our families move to our winter pasture. You can learn and sing more songs to me next time we meet."

She modestly replied, "I'm stupid and probably can't learn many songs. My mother taught me the song I just sang for many days. I easily forgot the lyrics, and my mother said I was stupid."

Big Head suddenly stood up, ran from Little Girl, and turned to look back to see if Little Girl was coming to attack him as he peed. There she was, pushing toward him, and soon she succeeded in playfully throwing him on the ground.

A month later, Little Girl's family arrived at her family's autumn pasture. Her mother asked her to enter as she stood at the tent entrance. Little Girl came inside and asked, "Mother, what's packed on that horse?"

"Our neighbor's grandmother passed away. It's her corpse."

Little Girl had never seen a corpse and peeked through her family's tent door. She saw a man riding a horse and leading a packed horse behind him. She could see the pack horse carrying something wrapped in white cloth.

Her mother was chanting scriptures and holding a string of beads in her hand but then paused and said, "Don't look at it."

Little Girl reluctantly walked to her mother, sitting near the stove.

"Don't sing at home or in the mountains. Our neighbors are mourning, and we should consider their feelings."

Little Girl nodded and sat by mother, who added, "Death is unpredictable. Chant as many scriptures as possible before you die. If you don't chant scriptures, you'll walk in the thick darkness after you die and be lost in the darkness. If you chant many scriptures, it will lighten the darkness."

Little Girl was frightened and immediately chanted mantras. She then said, "I don't have prayer beads. I need a string of beads."

"You don't need a string of prayer beads. You're a child."

"I need them," she insisted, interrupting her mother's chanting and grabbing a string of her prayer beads.

Little Girl chanted mantras the next day while holding a string of prayer beads and herding her family's yaks on a small hill. She assumed light would guide her soul in the darkness after she died. At night, she reported to her mother that she had recited mantras all day, earning her mother's praise and encouraging her to persist.

Little Girl sobbed one night after her mother scolded her for leaving her family's yaks on the mountain. She dried her eyes with the back of her hand as her mother put several pieces of dried yak dung into the scoop. Piously chanting mantras while blowing over the yak dung in the scoop, she pulled a tent rope through the upper part of the tent, secured it to the tent fabric, and put the scoop handle between the rope and the tent cloth, so the scoop was covered by tent cloth at the tent top.

Little Girl looked at the scoop and asked, "Mother, why did you do that?"

Without looking at her, her mother answered, "Put yak dung representing yaks in a scoop, chant scripture, and blow over the dung if you leave yaks on the mountains at night. Wolves and thieves won't see the yaks left on the mountain once tent cloth covers the dung in the scoop."

Little Girl looked at her mother, "Next time, I'll not leave any yaks on the mountains."

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Winter came. The tribal families all moved to their winter pastures.

Little Girl was unhappy Big Head's family didn't return to the winter pasture because they had herded yaks together since their families began sharing the winter pasture. Little Girl now herded her family's yaks on the mountains alone, pulled the upper part of her robe over her head, and slept each time she was bored to death while herding. She did not chant scriptures or sing. Wolves attacked her family's yaks and killed one while she was napping one afternoon. Her mother scolded and beat her when she reported what had happened. From that day on, Little Girl dared not nap, and wolves killed no more yaks. Her neighbors commented she would be a great yak herder like her mother, her mother was proud of her, and Little Girl was proud of herself for being a good herder.

Big Head's family eventually returned to the winter pasture, and Little Girl and Big Head herded together again. While sitting on a mountaintop as yaks grazed below them, Little Girl asked, "Why did your family only return to winter pasture yesterday?"

"My family moved to my older sister's land a month after we moved to the autumn pasture."

"Why did your family move there?"

"My sister's mother-in-law got sick when my sister was six months pregnant. Sister's husband took his mother to the hospital, so Sister needed my family's help. Father herded both families' yaks, and Mother helped Sister do house chores."

Big Head looked toward the mountain ranges topped with clouds above and meandering rivers below and gazed at the yaks peacefully grazing on rich grass. "I have not heard you sing for months. You sing very well. Please sing the song you sang last time we were together."

Little Girl was uncomfortable, put her head down, and murmured, "I can't. I forgot the song's lyrics and melody."

"How's it possible to forget the song in a few months? You're lying!"

"I forgot. I haven't sung it for months."

"You have a nice voice and sang that song well. Ask your mother, and she'll teach you."

Little Girl nodded.

Little Girl's mother handed her brother a bowl of milk tea and offered him a plate of boiled meat and a knife a bit later. She poured herself tea and took a piece of meat from a basin beside her.

Turning to him, she said, "Your daughter is young and can remarry, so don't worry about her marriage. She's nice. A good man will marry her."

After chewing a piece of meat, her brother replied, "It's all my fault. I thought her ex-husband was good and told her to marry him."

"It's OK. Don't worry. Your family is rich, and many good men want to marry your daughter. No good man will marry my daughter since my family is not rich."

"It's too early to think about your daughter's marriage. She's a little girl."

"She's different with no father to find her a good spouse."

"My friend is a very good man. His family is not rich, but he has two sons. Both are good boys and about Little Girl's age. It's possible to arrange a marriage between Little Girl and one of his sons."

"Great! Now I won't worry much about her marriage."

They continued chatting until he left shortly after the meal.

Little Girl and her mother went to bed after supper. Little Girl hesitated, "Mother, I forgot the song you taught me. Please teach me again."

"Let me sleep. I'll teach you later."

"Teach me tonight."

"Why do you want to learn it tonight?"

"I promised Big Head I'd sing it to him tomorrow. He said I have a nice voice and wants to hear that song again."

"You are troublesome. Let me sleep!" her mother scolded, but she was pleased and taught her the song again anyway.

Little Girl learned it quickly, impressing her mother. Little

Girl was so happy imagining Big Head enjoying her song the following day that sleep did not come until midnight.

TIBETAN TERMS

gu ru 'phrin las ཀུ་རུ་འཕྲིན་ལས།
rtsam pa རྩམ་པ།
sgrol ma སྒྲོལ་མ།

CHINESE TERM

Gerichengli 格日成立